

Elevational Gradients of epigeal spider (Araneae) and beetle (Carabidae and Tenebrionidae) diversity across the Western Soutpansberg Mountain: space, area and environment.

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Introduction

Spider and beetles play a major role in biodiversity ecosystem (Lassau *et al.*, 2005). They are good indicators since they respond rapidly to change as compared to vertebrate indicators, they are abundant and easy to catch (Petillon, *et al.*, 2006). This study is part of long term studies that are required in order to have a clear sense of the pace and the effect that the change in environmental conditions might have on biodiversity (Longino & Colwell 2011). Insect fauna is among the taxa that are poorly understood with reference to climate change and elevational gradients (Jennie *et al.*, 2006).

Therefore spiders and beetles are chosen to find out about the influence of gradient on their distribution.

Objectives

- To determine how epigeal spider and beetle composition differ between the altitudinal sites
- To examine how restricted species are to the major vegetation types
- To Investigate environmental variables, which underlie differences between assemblages and specificity of species
- To Identify Indicator species for each of the elevational sites

Study area

Materials and

The study was conducted along the North-South elevational gradient (800 – 1700 m a.s.l., 11 sites, 4 replicates, 10 pitfalls per site) which is centered over the Lajuma research station in the Soutpansberg, Limpopo. We used pitfall trapping method to catch the ground dwelling invertebrates. We also sampled the vertical and horizontal distribution of vegetation as set forth by Botes *et al.* 2006. 1 m² grid was placed in each pitfall trap and percentage of four soil categories *viz.* vegetation, leaf litter, exposed rock and bare ground were estimated, while vertical vegetation was measured by estimating foliage height profiles by measuring vegetation heights at four points at 90° angles on a 1.5 radius centered at each trap

Results and Discussion

Discussion

As expected the study revealed that species have preferences of sites, only few of those seem to be able to be tolerant of gradient as they can move from high elevation to lower elevation and vice versa. There is a clear restriction of species and that is a results of gradients and temperature along the mountain (Thiele, 1977). And there was a clear separation of northern spiders to southern spiders. Vegetation and soil seem to structure the distribution of spiders, therefore their distribution mainly depend on those axes and this may be because they are highly specialised habitat quality indicators while temperature and exposed rock seem to be the critical thing to hinder spiders distribution across the mountain (Bonte *et al.*, 2002).

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Vhuhwaho Gelebe, Caswel Munyai, Audrey Raidani, Lavhelesani Simba and Jerry Molepo for help with field work, University of Venda for logistic support. I am very grateful to my supervisor supervisor Dr. S. H. Foord for his assistance throughout the study. We are very grateful to Prof. I. Ghaiger for granting us permission to work on there property. Financial assistance for this project was provided by the DST-NRF Centre for Invasion Biology and University of Venda.